

PROGNOSTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CERVICAL INSUFFICIENCY IN PREGNANT WOMEN

Tilavova G.Y.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

gulshodatilavova1@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343859>

Relevance. The problem of cervical incompetence is becoming increasingly relevant, not only from a medical and biological perspective but also due to its social and economic importance. Preterm infants account for 70% of perinatal deaths and 65-75% of infant mortality. The rates of infant mortality are 8-13 times higher in preterm births compared to term births. According to data, the frequency of cervical incompetence ranges from 0.2% to 2%, accounting for 8-9% of all preterm births. Cervical cerclage is accepted as an effective intervention for pregnancies where a history of previous pregnancy loss or extreme premature delivery indicates a risk of cervical insufficiency.

Research Objective: To study the prognostic criteria for pregnancy outcomes in cases of cervical incompetence, improve diagnostic effectiveness, and enhance forecasting capabilities to prevent complications.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 20 women who underwent cervical cerclage (main group), 15 pregnant women identified with a risk of preterm birth without cervical incompetence (comparison group), and 15 healthy pregnant women (control group). Their anamnesis, medical-social data, instrumental, and laboratory indicators were collected and analyzed comparatively.

Results: In the main group, 45% of the women underwent surgical cerclage, while 55% received hormonal therapy. Their reproductive age distribution was as follows: early reproductive age – 2%, optimal reproductive age – 50%, and late reproductive age – 46%. Additionally, upon studying their anamnesis, it was found that 6 women (30%) had their first pregnancy, 8 women (40%) had a second pregnancy, and 6 women (30%) had multiple pregnancies (4 or more). Among those who received prophylactic cerclage, one woman had a complex medical history and underwent the procedure during the 12-15 weeks of pregnancy. Six women had cerclage performed between the 16th and 20th weeks of pregnancy.

In two other cases, emergency cerclage was performed between the 20th and 24th weeks due to a sharp decrease in cervical length and the risk of amniotic membrane rupture. For hormonal therapy, 11 women were selected. Their age distribution was: early reproductive age – 27.27%, optimal reproductive age – 36.36%, and late reproductive age – 36.36%. Among these women, 5 (45.45%) had their first pregnancy, 4 (36.36%) had a second pregnancy, and 2 (18.18%) had multiple pregnancies (4 or more). Of these women, 36.36% received vaginal progesterone, while 63.63% received it orally. According to the study results, among the women who underwent cerclage,

66.67% delivered after the 38th week, while 22.22% delivered between the 36th and 37th weeks. In 11.11% of cases, the pregnancy ended prematurely without reaching term.

In the progesterone therapy group, delivery occurred between the 36th and 37th weeks in 27.27% of cases, while in 63.63%, it occurred after the 37th week. In 9% of cases, delivery occurred before term.

In the comparison group, cervical incompetence was identified as the cause of miscarriage in 26.67% due to hormonal changes, in 20% due to uterine anomalies (such as fibroids or polyps), in 40% due to various infections, and in 13.33% due to late reproductive age (over 40 years).

While the two groups' associations with cervical operations were comparable in magnitude, nulliparous women's associations with prior miscarriages were significantly larger, particularly in multi-fetal gestations. In contrast, the independent connection between ICI and the history of prior losses was similar in singleton and multifetal pregnancies, and the association between ICI and multi-fetal gestation was significantly smaller for parous women, when further adjustments were made for characteristics associated to prior births.

Conclusions: The study results indicate that performing cerclage between the 16th and 20th weeks of pregnancy significantly increases the likelihood of carrying the pregnancy to at least the 37th week when cervical incompetence is diagnosed. It was found that vaginal administration of progesterone is 45% more effective than oral administration. The risk of miscarriage without cervical incompetence is primarily associated with hormonal changes and infections in the genital area.

Reference:

1. Meng L, Öberg S, Sandström A, Wang C, Reilly M. Identification of risk factors for incident cervical insufficiency in nulliparous and parous women: a population-based case-control study. *BMC Med.* 2022 Oct 12;20(1):348. doi: 10.1186/s12916-022-02542-7. PMID: 36221132; PMCID: PMC9555073.
2. Clark NV, Einarsson JI. Laparoscopic abdominal cerclage: a highly effective option for refractory cervical insufficiency. *Fertil Steril.* 2020 Apr;113(4):717-722. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2020.02.007. Epub 2020 Mar 5. PMID: 32147177.
3. Gupta S, Einarsson JI. Laparoscopic Abdominal Cerclage. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am.* 2022 Jun;49(2):287-297. doi: 10.1016/j.ogc.2022.02.010. PMID: 35636809.
4. Nath I. D., Abdurazakova M. RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF UTERINE FIBROIDS: ADVANCING MINIMALLY INVASIVE TREATMENT FOR WOMEN // Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2025. – Т. 4. – №. 13. – С. 17-21.

5. Dilshodovna A. M., Sattarovna B. G., Saidakhmadovna R. N. The Role of Chronic Cholecystitis in the Development of Obstetric Complications //American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences. – 2024. – T. 14. – №. 2. – C. 532-536.
6. Babadjanova G. S. et al. Peculiarities of the Pregnancy in Women with Hepatobiliary System Pathology //Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology. – 2020. – T. 14. – №. 4.
7. Nath I. D., Dilshodovna A. M. RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF UTERINE FIBROIDS: A REVIEW OF TECHNIQUES, EFFICACY, AND OUTCOMES //Web of Scientists and Scholars: Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 4. – C. 28-37.

